

SUPPLIER QUALITY ASSURANCE (SQA) A CASE STUDY AT URIL(DAWLANCE)

Submitted in Partial Fulfillment of the Requirements

For the Degree of

Bachelor of Industrial Engineering & Management

By:

Name	Roll Number
Farrukh Zaman (Group Leader)	10IN46
Muhammad Abid (Assistant G. L.)	10IN50
Muhammad Zubair	10IN89
Abbas Ali Lakho	10-09IN93

Supervised By:

Engr. Muhammad Ali Khan

Department of Industrial Engineering & Management

Mehran University of Engineering & Technology, Jamshoro

2013

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We dedicate to our own Parents

Mehran University of Engineering & Technology, Jamshoro

Certificate

This is to certify that the work presented in this project report/Thesis on “**Supplier Quality Assurance (SQA) A case study at Dawlance**”, is written and completed by the following students themselves, under the supervision of **Engr. Muhammad Ali Khan**

Name	Roll Number
Farrukh Zaman(Group Leader)	10IN46
Muhammad Abid(Assistant G.L.)	10IN50
Muhammad Zubair	10IN89
Abbas Ali Lakho	10-09IN93

Engr. Muhammad Ali Khan

Project/Thesis Supervisor

External Examiner

Chairman,

Department of Industrial Engineering & Management

Table of Content

Description	-----	Page
Acknowledgement	-----	Vi
List of Abbreviations	-----	Vii
List of Tables	-----	viii
List of Figures	-----	Ix
Abstract	-----	Xi
Chapter 1	Introduction-----	1
1.1	Overview-----	1
1.2	Introduction To Company-----	1
1.3	URIL (Dawlance) product	3
1.4	Division Of Department-----	3
1.5	Problem Statement	8
1.6	Aims and Objectives-----	8
Chapter 2	Literature Review-----	9
2.1	Supplier Quality Assurance (SQA)-----	9
2.2	Role of Supplier Quality Assurance-----	9
2.3	Objectives of Supplier Quality Assurance-----	10
2.4	Benefits of Supplier Quality Assurance-----	10
2.5	Supplier Quality Assurance activities-----	11
2.6	General inspection/test requirement of SQA-----	11
2.7	Supplier corrective action-----	12
2.8	Supplier monitoring-----	12
2.9	Certificate of Conformance-----	12
2.10	Best practices of Supplier Quality Assurance-----	13
2.11	Classification of suppliers-----	14
2.12	Supplier selection criteria-----	16
2.13	The Analytic Hierarchy process (AHP)-----	16
2.14	Evaluation of Suppliers-----	17
2.15	Inspection in SQA -----	18
2.16	Method of inspection -----	18
2.17	Sampling -----	18
2.18	Sampling inspection -----	19
2.19	Benefits of sampling Inspection-----	19
2.20	Sampling plan-----	19
2.21	Classification of Sampling inspection-----	20
2.22	Refrigerator compressor -----	21

2.23	Types of refrigerator compressors-----	22
2.24	Parts of the compressor-----	23
Chapter 3	Research Methodology-----	26
3.1	Research Purpose-----	26
3.2	Research Approach -----	26
Chapter 4	Case study-----	28
4.1	Introduction to Supplier Quality Assurance at URIL-----	28
4.2	Working Procedure of SQA-----	30
4.3	Problems in Inspection at SQA-----	40
4.4	Sampling Plan-----	40
4.5	Suppliers-----	41
4.6	Focus of Study-----	41
4.7	Compressor-----	41
4.8	Workflow of Compressor and its inspection-----	42
4.9	Defected Compressors-----	44
4.10	Compressor Defects-----	45
4.11	Data of Compressors Defects-----	45
Chapter 5	Analysis of Data -----	58
5.1	Comparison of supplier quantity with defected quantity among compressor companies-----	58
5.2	Comparison of defected quantity among three companies-----	59
5.3	Analysis of different defects with respect to total defects in each compressor company-----	60
5.4	Analysis of Defects company wise-----	70
5.5	Analysis of individual defect-----	72
5.6	Main reasons for defects -----	73
5.7	Discussion-----	74
Chapter 6	Conclusion and Recommendation-----	76
6.1	Conclusion-----	76
6.2	Recommendation from Research-----	77
6.3	Scope of Research-----	78
References	-----	79

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We wish for better future for **URIL** (Dawlance) where we completed our Final year thesis work and we learned a lot which will help us in our future.

LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

SQA	Supplier Quality Assurance
URIL	United Refrigeration Industries Limited
COC	Certificate of Compliance
MRS	Material Receiving Slip
ITI	Inspection and Test instruction
STR	Sample Test Report
RMDN	Rejected Material Disposition Notice
QDR	Quality Defect Report
MSR	Material Status Report
C-Form	Check Form
C of C	Certificate of Conformance

LIST OF TABLES

Table 2.1	Classification of Supplier-----	14
Table 4.1	Sampling Plan-----	40
Table 4.2	Detail of defects of all three refrigerator compressor companies-----	46
Table 4.3	Table of month-wise detail of total supplier quantity and total defected quantity of Panasonic Compressors-----	47
Table 4.4	Table of month-wise detail of total supplier quantity and total defected quantity of Denfoss Compressors-----	51
Table 4.5	Table of month-wise detail of total supplier quantity and total defected quantity of Wanbao Compressors-----	55

LIST OF FIGURES

Fig 1.1	Graph of Refrigerator market share-----	2
Fig 1.2	Graph of Freezer market share-----	2
Fig 1.3	URIL product-----	3
Fig 1.4	Organogram of United Refrigeration Industries Limited-----	7
Fig 2.1	Best practices for supplier auditing-----	13
Fig 4.1	Organogram of Supplier Quality Assurance (SQA) Department of URIL-----	29
Fig 4.2	Flow chart of inspection procedure of SQA-----	33
Fig 4.3	Document of certificate of compliance-----	34
Fig 4.4	Document of sample test report-----	35
Fig 4.5	Document of C-form-----	36
Fig 4.6	Document of rejected material and disposition notice-----	37
Fig 4.7	Document of material status report-----	38
Fig 4.8	Document of quality defect report-----	39
Fig 4.9	Flow chart of inspection procedure of compressor-----	43
Fig 4.10	Picture of compressors lot at SQA departments-----	44
Fig 4.11	Graph of Panasonic total supplier and defected quantity-----	48
Fig 4.12	Graph of Panasonic compressor defects in July-12-----	49
Fig 4.13	Graph of Panasonic compressor defects in Aug-12-----	49
Fig 4.14	Graph of Panasonic compressor defects in Sep-12-----	49
Fig 4.15	Graph of Panasonic compressor defects in Oct-12-----	49
Fig 4.16	Graph of Panasonic compressor defects in Nov-12-----	50
Fig 4.17	Graph of Panasonic compressor defects in Dec-12-----	50
Fig 4.18	Graph of Panasonic compressor defects in Jan-13-----	50
Fig 4.19	Graph of Panasonic compressor defects in Feb-13-----	50
Fig 4.20	Graph of Panasonic compressor defects in Mar-13-----	50
Fig 4.21	Graph of Panasonic compressor defects in Jun-13-----	50
Fig 4.22	Graph of Panasonic compressor defects in July-13-----	51
Fig 4.23	Graph of Denfoss total supplier and defected quantity-----	52
Fig 4.24	Graph of Denfoss compressor defects in July-12-----	53
Fig 4.25	Graph of Denfoss compressor defects in Sep-12-----	53
Fig 4.26	Graph of Denfoss compressor defects in Oct-12-----	53
Fig 4.27	Graph of Denfoss compressor defects in Nov-12-----	53
Fig 4.28	Graph of Denfoss compressor defects in Feb-13-----	54
Fig 4.29	Graph of Denfoss compressor defects in Apr-13-----	54
Fig 4.30	Graph of Denfoss compressor defects in May-13-----	54
Fig 4.31	Graph of Denfoss compressor defects in Jun-13-----	54
Fig 4.32	Graph of Denfoss compressor defects in July-13-----	54
Fig 4.33	Graph of Wanbao total supplier and defected quantity-----	56
Fig 4.34	Graph of Wanbao Compressor defects in July-12-----	57
Fig 4.35	Graph of Wanbao Compressor defects in Sep-12-----	57
Fig 4.36	Graph of Wanbao Compressor defects in Oct-12-----	57
Fig 4.37	Graph of Wanbao Compressor defects in Dec-12-----	57

Fig 5.1	Graph of Comparison of supplier quantity with defected quantity-----	58
Fig 5.2	Graph of Trend of defected quantity of three companies----	59
Fig 5.3	Graph of Compressor defects in July-12-----	60
Fig 5.4	Graph of Compressor defects in Aug-12-----	61
Fig 5.5	Graph of Compressor defects in Sep-12-----	62
Fig 5.6	Graph of Compressor defects in Oct-12-----	63
Fig 5.7	Graph of Compressor defects in Nov-12-----	64
Fig 5.8	Graph of Compressor defects in Dec-12-----	65
Fig 5.9	Graph of Compressor defects in Jan-13-----	65
Fig 5.10	Graph of Compressor defects in Feb-13-----	66
Fig 5.11	Graph of Compressor defects in Mar-13-----	67
Fig 5.12	Graph of Compressor defects in Apr-13-----	67
Fig 5.13	Graph of Compressor defects in May-13-----	68
Fig 5.14	Graph of Compressor defects in Jun-13-----	68
Fig 5.15	Graph of Compressor defects in July-13-----	69
Fig 5.16	Graph of Panasonic defects trend-----	70
Fig 5.17	Graph of Denfoss defects trend-----	71
Fig 5.18	Graph of Wanbao defects trend-----	71
Fig 5.19	Graph of Mean of individual compressor defects-----	72

ABSTRACT

Quality represents a survival in the competitive world. Without quality it is impossible for any organization to compete in the market. Supplier Quality Assurance (SQA) surveillances the supplier quality for the satisfaction of their customer needs and for effective and efficient product quality. SQA in URIL (Dawlance) inspects and tests the supplier material. The concerned inspector collects sample which is according to sample plan and inspects the material as per inspection and test instruction (ITI). The aim of study was to understand the operations of SQA and analyze the defects of refrigerator compressor from July12 to July13. A case study was done; the focus of study was refrigerator compressor defects. For achieving the objectives, the research methodology for collecting the data was observation, interview and organizational data. The data was collected through SQA department of the organization. Compressors in URIL were imported from three suppliers which were Panasonic, Denfoss and Wanbao. The sampling of compressor was five pieces per lot taken randomly. The defects in compressors identified were; high ampere, rigidity fault, pipe crack, pipe leak, compressor sound, compressor not start and leak & under charge. Through the interview of the experienced personnel in the organization the reasons for defects were sought. During analysis, month-wise detail of defects, mean of individual defect and trend of defects in each company was obtained. The study concluded that the mean frequency of pipe leak was the highest followed by high ampere, pipe crack and rigidity while the defects of compressor sound, compressor not start and leak & undercharge were occurred rarely during the study period. The trends of defects showed that in Panasonic high ampere, while in Denfoss and Wanbao, pipe leak was seen most frequently. The study recommended that high ampere defect, pipe leak, pipe crack and rigidity fault can be avoided by minimizing overcharging, careful handling, using superior quality of material and monitoring the short circuit.

CHAPTER # 1

INTRODUCTION

1.1 OVERVIEW:

There is a growing world-wide recognition of the critical relationship between quality and international competitiveness. Across the globe companies are increasingly adopting quality as a cultural theme for improving their performance (J.M. Juran). The efficient production of the quality that the market expects (Deming). Quality Assurance is the planned or systematic actions necessary to provide enough confidence that a product will satisfy the given requirements for quality. Supplier Quality Assurance (SQA) deals with the activity for supplier quality surveillance. All over the world SQA play a vital role for investigation of supplier material means the checking of material and evaluation of supplier till the corrective action for the rectification of defects in material. Therefore Supplier Quality Assurance has very significant role in any organization. SQA directly deal with the sampling, testing and inspection of incoming supplier material according to the required specification of the organization. If any discrepancy takes place in this area then the organization will suffer uncountable losses. The SQA role and its importance are clear and well established therefore we choose it as our topic of study.

1.2 INTRODUCTION TO COMPANY:

United Refrigeration Industries Limited (URIL) means Dawlance was established in 1980, it is the premiere Home appliances company in Pakistan. . Firstly, they were imported the refrigerator of about one year. Dawlance started refrigerator production in 1981, deep freezer production in 1988. Dawlance started production of aero design series in 1996. Dawlance started production of upright freezer in 1997. Dawlance was certified for ISO 9001 and for ISO 14000 in the years 1999 and 2001 respectively. In the year of 2007 Dawlance launched reflection series refrigerator. The latest series of Dawlance is health zone, started in the year of 2010. However they are importing compressor and evaporator. Apart from its local production, the company is presently engaged in import of Frost-free refrigerator.

Dawlance delivers the highest value to its customers by giving better performance and nice features of the product. Dawlance places its top priority on the satisfaction of its customers, partners and employees. Over these years Dawlance has not only developed the largest dealer's network but also established the largest after sales service setup across Pakistan by setting 20 branches, 40 contract Workshop mobile units in all major cities, one central office at Karachi & one regional office at Lahore. Dawlance has 16 warehouses all over Pakistan. The percentage of imported parts is 30% and percentage of local and in-house parts is 70%. Its refrigerator market share is 63% and of chest freezer is 36% as shown in graph below:

Fig 1.1

Fig 1.2

1.3 URIL (Dawlance) Product:

The product of URIL is shown in fig 1.3 below:

919969188

9175

9170

Fig 1.3 (URIL product)

1.4 DIVISION OF DEPARTMENT:

URIL (Dawlance) is divided into following various departments as mention and discuss further. Also the organogram of the company is shown in fig 1.4

-
- Finance department
 - HR department
 - Procurement and Purchasing department
 - Design and Development department
 - Plant Engineering department
 - PPC department
 - Maintenance department
 - Manufacturing department
 - Supplier Quality Assurance department
 - Quality control and Audit department
 - Field Quality Control And Audit Department
 - Safety and Security department
 - M.I.S department

1.4.1 FINANCE DEPARTMENT:

Finance department deals with all the financial transaction either pay to the supplier and employees and else. It also deals with the preparation of budget, management of investment of the company and management of taxes.

1.4.2 HUMAN RESOURCE DEPARTMENT:

HR department deals with the recruitment and selection of the employees. Also deals with the training and development, performance evaluation, promotion and reward to the employees. It also deals problems related with the employees.

1.4.3 PROCUREMENT AND PURCHASING DEPARTMENT:

Procurement and purchasing department deal with the finding of new supplier and purchasing of the material. It provides assistance to all departments of the company in the procurement of the equipment and supplies.

1.4.4 DESIGN AND DEVELOPMENT DEPARTMENT:

Design and Development department deals with the product review, modification in in-house parts and product failure analysis.

1.4.5 PLANT ENGINEERING DEPARTMENT:

Plant Engineering Department deals with the Machine erection, Machine installation and purchasing of spare parts.

1.4.6 PRODUCTION AND PLANNING CONTROL DEPARTMENT:

Production and Planning control department deals with the Production Planning and Material management by generating Master Production Schedule and Bill of material. It coordinates departmental activities and maintains flow of production steady.

1.4.7 MAINTENANCE DEPARTMENT:

Maintenance department ensures the smooth operation of all machinery. It deals with the trouble shooting of machines. Maintenance department also deals with the maintenance and routine inspection of machines and equipment.

1.4.8 MANUFACTURING DEPARTMENT:

Manufacturing department deals with the manufacturing of the product according to the production plan. It deals with the efficient flow of manufacturing operations.

1.4.9 SUPPLIER QUALITY ASSURANCE DEPARTMENT:

Supplier quality assurance department deals with all the activities related with the sampling, testing and inspection of the incoming supplier material quality. Supplier quality assurance deals with the measurement, planning and evaluation of supplier quality relating responsibility.

1.4.10 QUALITY CONTROL AND AUDIT DEPARTMENT:

Quality control and audit department deals with the Internal process verification, product verification and internal departmental procedure audit and control of quality.

1.4.11 FIELD QUALITY AND AUDIT DEPARTMENT:

Field quality and audit department deals with the field audit of product, service centre examination. It deals with product performance feedback, field performance.

1.4.12 SAFETY AND SECURITY DEPARTMENT:

Safety and Security department deals with the personal protective equipment, monitoring the safety procedures and maintaining the in-plant security. It also deals with the implementation of effective security program

1.4.13 MIS DEPARTMENT:

MIS department deals with the computer software/server and database management of the organization. It deals with the data processing. MIS department with the data storage, analysis and will make it available to the manager when required.

Fig 1.4(Organogram of URIL)

1.5 PROBLEM STATEMENT:

Increased competition in the market caused every organization to work according to market requirements. URIL (Dawlance) produces refrigerator although they also get some parts from supplier including compressors. Compressor is the heart of any refrigerator (function wise). URIL (Dawlance) is importing compressors from three companies namely Panasonic, Denfoss & Wanbao from Malaysia, Slovakia and China respectively. Quality checking of imported compressors of different companies is not an easy task. In URIL (Dawlance) there is a department of Supplier quality assurance for checking the quality of incoming material. These compressors may have some defected quantity and these possible defects may be high ampere, rigidity fault, pipe leak, pipe crack, compressor sound, compressor not start, under charge. These are discussed in detail in the next chapters.

1.6 AIM AND OBJECTIVES:

1.6.1 AIM:

To understand the operations of supplier quality assurance (SQA) and analyzes the defects of refrigerator compressor in United Refrigeration Industries Limited (Dawlance).

1.6.2 OBJECTIVES:

1. To understand the inspection procedure of Supplier Quality Assurance.
2. To understand the inspection procedure of Refrigerator compressor.
3. To analyze the data of refrigerator compressor.

CHAPTER #2

LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 SUPPLIER QUALITY ASSURANCE (SQA):

The supplier quality assurance is related with the planning, measurement and control of supplier quality responsibility relating surveillance. The Supplier Quality Assurance applies all techniques related to inspection and testing of material at the time of receiving. Supplier quality assurance builds a confidence in supplier's ability to deliver a good product or service that will satisfy the customer's needs. Achievable through interactive relationship between the supplier and customer, it aims at ensuring the product's fits to the customer's requirement with little or no adjustment or inspection.

J.M.Juran divides the supplier quality assurance process into nine steps [4]:

1. Definition of the product's quality requirements.
2. Evaluation of alternative suppliers.
3. Selection of the most appropriate suppliers.
4. Conduction of joint quality planning
5. Cooperation during relationship period.
6. Validation of conformance to requirements.
7. Certification of the qualified suppliers.
8. Conduction of the quality improvement plans.
9. Creation and use of supplier ratings

2.2 ROLE OF SUPPLIER QUALITY ASSURANCE (SQA):

Supplier Quality Assurance (SQA) plays a vital role in any organization. The role of SQA is [4]:

1. Identification of any quality problem in inspection.
2. Verification that quality problems have been alleviated and corrected.

3. To communicate with the supplier (also include feedback), receiving inspection, supplier evaluation, corrective action verification at supplier premises.
4. Responsible for all quality improvement issues related to vendors & suppliers, assesses of new suppliers materials.
5. Implement corrective action on non-conforming material of suppliers.
6. Provide procurement control documentation that will be traceable to ensure that the quality standards have been met.
7. Responsible for Supplier- organization relationship management.
8. The SQA systematically manages customer satisfaction by ensuring that the product meets the needs of the customer through working directly with its purchasing department.

2.3 OBJECTIVES OF SUPPLIER QUALITY ASSURANCE (SQA):

The basic Supplier Quality Assurance objectives are:

1. To assist Purchasing to realize the greater combined purchasing opportunity of working through the entire organization,
2. To assist Purchasing to achieve the optimized supplier base, and
3. To assist Purchasing to consequently create the most effective network of alliances with the best suppliers in the industry.[7]

2.4 BENEFITS OF SUPPLIER QUALITY ASSURANCE (SQA):

Supplier Quality Assurance (SQA) has a number of benefits due to its importance in any organization. The benefits of SQA are given below [7]:

1. SQA help the organization manage/reduce risks when dealing with suppliers.
2. SQA help in supplier development but is dependent on the organizations objectives for their suppliers and available resources.
3. SQA minimize possible defects through identification in inspection of supplier provided parts.

2.5 SUPPLIER QUALITY ASSURANCE (SQA) ACTIVITIES:

SQA have a uniform handling of specific quality matters, such as [9]:

1. Quality improvement activities and programs
2. Specific quality problems
3. Quality target setting
4. Quality assurance within joint product development projects.
5. Preparation & updating the Incoming Inspection plans.
6. Coordinating the incoming inspection activity.
7. Weekly communication of rejections to supplier.
8. Weekly supplier quality related reporting.
9. Day- to-day Quality problem troubleshooting with suppliers processes at their end.

2.6 GENERAL INSPECTION / TEST REQUIREMENTS OF SQA:

Inspection and test should be carried out in accordance with the organization Specification/ requirements. The SQA use equipment that is appropriate for the required tolerances and characteristics of the supplier parts to be tested.

2.6.1 VISUAL INSPECTION:

It is necessary to carry out “visual inspection” the criteria for this will be defined by the organization.

2.6.2 DIMENSIONAL INSPECTION / MATERIAL TESTING:

The SQA must have the necessary equipment to conduct the required dimensional inspection / tests. The SQA will maintain a calibration system which includes gauges, tools and fixtures used to verify conformity to requirements of the organization.

2.6.3 RIGHT OF ACCESS:

The SQA of any organization reserves the right of access to the supplier’s premises during the course of the contract. This may include access to the supplier’s sub tier facility.

2.6.4 SOURCE INSPECTION:

Any items and quality documentation covered by purchase order maybe subject to sourceinspection prior to shipment. In order to accommodate source inspectionrepresentatives, the supplier will make facilities, equipment, inspectionrecords and assistance readily available. Source inspection will notreplace supplier inspection activities. [2]

2.7 SUPPLIER CORRECTIVE ACTION:

The supplier is responsible for implementing a quality system capable ofresolving problems affecting quality and correcting those conditions and SQA will monitors the supplier corrective action. Thesupplier's corrective action should be documented and as a minimuminclude[2]:

1. Identification of root cause
2. An analysis of similar items that may be affected
3. A list of improvements and actions to prevent problem re occurrence
4. Records that are maintained and available to SQA(if required)

2.8 SUPPLIER MONITORING:

SQA continuously monitors the Supplier performance.It will measure the supplier's ability to meet organization requirements for product quality and delivery performance. Suppliers will be notified periodically of their performance. [2]

2.9 CERTIFICATE OF CONFORMANCE:

SQAauthorized person will sign the suppliers C of C signifying that allproducts have met the requirements of the organization purchase order includingany drawings or specifications.Thesupplier will submit a copy of his certificate of conformity with each shipment of material or products if the organization requires.[2]

2.10 BEST PRACTICES OF SQA:

SQA have many best practices for the surveillance of supplier. The best practices of SQA are discussed below.

2.10.1 SUPPLIER AUDIT:

Supplier Audits are one of the best ways to ensure that supplier is following the processes and procedures that you agreed to during the selection processes. The supplier audit identifies non-conformances in manufacturing process, shipment process, engineering change process, invoicing process and quality process at the supplier. After the audit, the supplier and SQA jointly identify corrective actions which must be implemented by the supplier within an agreed-upon timeframe. A future audit ensures that these corrective actions have been successfully implemented.

The following fig 2.1 shows the best practices process for supplier auditing.

Fig 2.1 (best practices for supplier auditing)

2.10.2 SUPPLIER SCORECARD:

Supplier Scorecards are one of the best techniques in using facts to rank the supplier's relative performance within the supply base and tracking improvement in supplier's quality over time. Scorecards also provide a data point into any future business negotiations. Following are the list of key operational metrics that leading manufacturers track in their supplier scorecard:[10]

1. PPM defects of Supplier Components
2. Average Response and Resolution time for Corrective actions
3. Rework Hours due to defected Supplier Components
4. Performance against benchmark
5. Relative ranking of supplier

2.11 CLASSIFICATION OF SUPPLIERS:

The organization decides the classification of supplier according to its ability to support the overall strategy. That means the ability to meet organization targets concerning Quality, Delivery, Cost, Environment, Engineering etc. The classification is communicated internally and is used as a tool in supply sourcing. The five general levels are described in the table 2.1 below: [9]

Classification	Description
Preferred Supplier	This is the level that each supplier is expected eventually to achieve. Only suppliers who have made a commitment to meet all the customer expectations will achieve this classification. Preferred Suppliers are characterized by a leadership position in Engineering, Quality, Cost and Delivery.

Active supplier	An Active supplier is used, if the Preferred suppliers cannot be used for specific reasons, as long as they fulfil organization minimum Requirements, e.g. are at least quality useable. Minimum expectation for this level is the completion of Quality Plans for all parts being purchased. Suppliers in this category may be Considered for new part development work.
Restricted Supplier (On Hold)	This category applies to suppliers who are having major problems either with quality or delivery or for some other reason. No new inquiries will be made and the supplier will not be involved in new projects. Any problem parts will be subjected to 100% inspection. If there is no improvement in an allotted time then the supplier could become disqualified.
Disqualified Supplier	This supplier does not fulfil organization minimum requirement. They will not receive any new business and the existing business will be phased out.
Potential Supplier	This supplier is not currently organization supplier, but is regarded as having the potential to become a preferred or active supplier.

Table 2.1

2.12 SUPPLIER SELECTION CRITERIA:

In 1966 Dickson presented a list of 23 criteria for supplier selection, the ranking of these criteria may be dependent upon the specific circumstances but Dickson suggested criteria and ranking which are given in table. These criteria do still cover most of the important factors up to present time. Traditionally the four criteria cost, quality, delivery and service are assumed to be an appropriate set and includes most of the criteria. [3]

- | | |
|---|--------------------------------|
| 1. Quality | 2. Management and organization |
| 3. Delivery | 4. Operating control |
| 5. Performance history | 6. Repair service |
| 7. Warranties and claim policies | 8. Attitude |
| 9. Production facilities and capacity | 10. Impression |
| 11. Price | 12. Packing ability |
| 13. Technical capability | 14. Labor relations record |
| 15. Financial status | 16. Geographical location |
| 17. Procedural compliance | 18. Amount of past business |
| 19. Communications system | 20. Training aids |
| 21. Reputation and position in industry | 22. Reciprocal arrangements |
| 23. Desire for business | |

2.13 THE ANALYTIC HIRARCHY PROCESS (AHP):

The AHP method is very suitable for supplier selection. The AHP is a process that is easy to use and the results may be very concrete and straightforward. Once the criteria and the weights set, the actual comparison between suppliers takes about 20 minutes using Expert Choice. This method is very fast with respect to the factors which may be included in the

Comparison and should imply better accuracy and more frequent evaluation of suppliers. Although the AHP has many inputs it does not cover everything. The results should be evaluated and compared with the purchasers' judgment and experience.

Ghodsypour & O'Brien (1998) use the AHP for supplier selection. The following steps are suggested:

1. Define the criteria for supplier selection.
2. Calculate the weights of the criteria.
3. Rate the alternative suppliers.
4. Compute the overall score of each supplier.
5. Build the linear model and maximize the total value of purchasing (TVP)[3]

2.14 EVALUATION OF SUPPLIERS:

Generally it has been observed that before becoming a supplier, an evaluation is performed by the purchaser together with the company. It contains general information about the firm, financial information, information of production and production techniques plus how the company manages quality and environmental issues. The qualification process might be based on a questionnaire filled in by the supplier denoted as simplified qualification. It might also be filled in onsite following the supplier assessment workbook, a full qualification. The supplier assessment workbook is a guide for what information together from the supplier. The full qualification renders in an evaluation based on five graded scales within the following areas [3]:

1. General information
2. Finance
3. Production/technique
4. Quality
5. Environment

2.15 INSPECTON IN SQA:

Any item or component or product which is manufactured is required to perform certain functions. Inspection is the process of measuring the quality of a product in terms of established standards. Inspection is the function to judge the quality of a product. Inspection in SQA is the art of applying tests, preferably by the aid of measuring appliances to observe whether a supplier item or product is within the specified limit of variability. The act of inspection serves two purposes. First, it separates defective components from non-defective ones and thus ensures the adequate quality of the product. Secondly, inspection locates defects in raw materials and flaws in processes which otherwise cause problems at the final stage. For example, detecting the parts, not having proper tolerances during processing itself will minimize the troubles arising at the time of assembly. [1]

2.16METHOD OF INSPECTION:

There are various methods of inspection for checking the quality of a product. Some of the methods of inspection are given below:

- Screening or 100% inspection
- Lot by Lot inspection
- Process Inspection

2.17SAMPLING:

A sampling is an act of drawing samples from a batch on random basis. Sampling depends upon statistical probability and therefore samples must be collected from all sides and different depths of the box containing the lot or batch (of component parts) so that every part has an equal chance of being selected. The samples should be collected at regular intervals (say every hour, every four hour, everyday etc.) from the entire production run. The purpose is to obtain a sample truly representative of the lot. [1]

2.18 SAMPLING INSPECTION:

Sampling inspection is a technique to determine whether a lot or population should be rejected or accepted on the basis of the number of defective parts found in a random sample drawn from the lot. If the numbers of defective parts exceed a predefined level, the lot is rejected. [1]

As compared to 100 percent inspection, the sampling inspection claims the following:

2.19 BENEFITS OF SAMPLING INSPECTION:

The various benefits of sampling inspection are given below:

1. It involves less amount of inspection to achieve a predecided degree of certainty about the quality.
2. It consumes less time, and is less expensive.
3. Fatigue and boredom incurred by the inspectors is much less, hence their operating efficiency remains high.
4. It is more accurate because in 100 percent inspection, errors get introduced because of the fatigue and boredom incurred by the inspectors due to large inspection work of repetitive nature.
5. Since fewer pieces are inspected, no damage is done to the remaining pieces of the lot as they are not handled.
6. In certain cases where the components are to be inspected by destructive testing or where a powder is to be chemically analyzed, 100 percent inspection can never be employed.
7. Rejection of a complete batch on the basis of a sample decidedly pressurizes for improvements in quality. [1]

2.20 SAMPLING PLAN:

A sampling plan is simply a decision rule which specifies how large a sample (n) should be taken and the allowable measurement, number or percentage (c) of defectives in the sample. If the items to be inspected are classified qualitatively according to an attribute,

such as good or bad, acceptable or not acceptable and so on, then the sampling plan is referred to as an attributes plan, and the probabilities of defectives in the parent population are estimated from discrete distribution such as the binomial and poisson. An attributes sampling plan might read as follows: select a random sample size $n=40$ and count the number of defectives C , if the number of defectives $C < 3$, accept the lot, otherwise reject it.

If the items to be inspected are classified quantitatively according to some measurable characteristics, they will require a variable sampling plan. Since variables plans necessitate the recoding of actual measurement instead simply say good or bad. They provide more information and require fewer inspections for the same degree of assurance than do comparable attributes plans.

2.21 CLASSIFICATION OF SAMPLING INSPECTION:

2.21.1 SAMPLING BY ATTRIBUTES:

Attribute (Yes or No) inspection is used to differentiate between a defective and a non-defective part and the part is rejected or accepted without using quantitative measures. For example, if out of a sample taken from a predefined number of bullets fire, the lot is accepted otherwise rejected. Attribute inspection is very important and also very common.

Firstly, attribute inspection is used where components are obviously defective and non-defective. Secondly, where it is very difficult and costly to measure the quality characteristics of a product, e.g., measuring the quality of paint on a refrigerator. Thirdly, attribute inspection finds applications where the manufacturer does not see any need to measure the exact job dimensions and he feels that go and no go type of inspection can serve his purpose, as in shafts, spindle or rings. The greatest amount of sampling inspection is done using attributes.

2.21.2 SAMPLING BY VARIABLES:

When inspection is carried out by measuring the quality characteristics of a product, for example its dimensions, i.e., diameter, length, thickness, weight, etc., it is called inspection by variables.

Variables involve the averages of measurements whereas attributes deal with percentages of parts rejected. Inspection using variables is mostly done on the shop floor and is important for the control of operations.

Inspection using variables is more detailed, contains more information, but involves higher inspection and other costs, per unit, as compared to attribute inspection.

The manufacturer has to decide at some stage which inspection to use, of course depending upon the requirements of his product.

2.21.3 LOT BY LOT SAMPLING INSPECTION:

The components are formed into lots and each lot is accepted or rejected on the basis of the quality of one or more samples drawn from the lot. The pieces in the samples may be inspected by using variables or attribute data.

2.21.4 CONTINUOUS SAMPLING INSPECTION:

In this system the current inspection results give an idea whether to go for sampling inspection or 100% inspection (i.e., screening inspection) for inspecting the next items.

[1]

2.22 REFRIGERATOR COMPRESSOR:

A refrigerator compressor is the center of the refrigeration cycle. It works as a pump to control the circulation of the refrigerant, and it adds pressure to the refrigerant, heating it up. The compressor also draws vapor away from the evaporator to maintain a lower pressure and lower temperature before sending it to the condenser. [5]

2.23 TYPES OF REFRIGERATOR COMPRESSORS:

The main types of refrigeration compressors are reciprocating, screw, scroll and centrifugal.

2.23.1 ROTARY SCREW COMPRESSORS:

Rotary screw compressors have screw spindles that compress the gas as it enters from the evaporator. The screw compressor features smooth operation and minimal maintenance requirements; typically these compressors only require changes in oil, the oil filter and the air/oil separator. There are two types of rotary screw compressors: single and twin.

2.23.2 RECIPROCATING COMPRESSORS:

A reciprocating compressor uses the reciprocating action of a piston inside a cylinder to compress refrigerant. As the piston moves downward, a vacuum is created inside the cylinder. Because the pressure above the intake valve is greater than the pressure below it, the intake valve is forced open and refrigerant is sucked into the cylinder. After the piston reaches its bottom position it begins to move upward. The intake valve closes, trapping the refrigerant inside the cylinder. As the piston continues to move upward it compresses the refrigerant, increasing its pressure. At a certain point the pressure exerted by the refrigerant forces the exhaust valve to open and the compressed refrigerant flows out of the cylinder. Once the piston reaches its top-most position, it starts moving downward again and the cycle is repeated.

2.23.3 SCROLL COMPRESSORS:

Scroll compressors work by moving one spiral element inside another stationary spiral to produce gas pockets that, as they become smaller, increase the pressure of the gas. During compression, several pockets are compressed at once. By maintaining an even number of balanced gas pockets on opposite sides, the compression forces inside the scroll balance and reduce vibration inside the compressor. This type of compressor uses the scroll design instead of a fixed cylinder or a piston or single-sided compression mechanism, eliminating wasted space in the compression chamber and eliminating the

need to compress gas again and again during the cycle (recompression). This reduces energy use.

2.23.4 CENTRIFUGAL COMPRESSORS:

Centrifugal compressors compress refrigerant gas through the centrifugal force created by rotors that spin at high speed. This energy is then sent to a diffuser, which converts a portion of it into increased pressure. It does this by expanding the region of the flow volume to slow the flow velocity of the working fluid. Diffusers may use airfoils, also known as vanes, to improve this. Centrifugal compressors are suited for compressing large volumes of gas to moderate pressure. [5]

2.24 PARTS OF THE COMPRESSOR:

The important parts of the reciprocating compressor are: cylinder, piston, piston rings, connecting rod, crankshaft, suction valve, discharge valve, suction port, discharge port etc. All these parts have been described in details below:

2.124.1 CYLINDER:

In small compressors the cylinder is made by directly boring into the main body of the compressor, which is usually made up of cast iron. In case of the large multi-cylinder compressors, the cylinder is made separately and it is fitted into the main body of the compressor. This type of cylinder is also called as the liner or sleeve. In such compressors if any of the cylinders gets worn out or damaged, it can be replaced easily by the new liner, without having to replace the whole compressor.

2.24.2 PISTON:

The piston performs upwards and downwards motion inside the cylinder, which is also called as the reciprocating motion. During its motion the piston enables suction and compression of the refrigerant. The piston is made of cast iron or aluminum. During its motion inside the cylinder the refrigerant should not leak through the gap between the cylinder walls and the piston to the crankcase, hence piston is covered with the piston rings. The piston rings are not required in the smaller compressors. The gap between the

piston and the cylinder is also filled with the lubricating oil, which also prevents the leakage of the compressed refrigerant to the crankcase.

2.24.3 PISTON RINGS:

The piston rings are circled around the piston. When the piston performs reciprocating motion inside the cylinder, it is the piston rings that come in contact with the walls of the cylinder. There is lots of friction between the cylinder walls and the piston rings, thus they have to be replaced from time-to-time for proper functioning of the compressor. This helps increasing the life of the piston and prevents replacement of the complete piston.

2.24.4 CRANKSHAFT:

The piston can perform reciprocating motion inside the cylinder because of the rotary motion of the crankshaft. The crankshaft is the main shaft of the compressor. On one side it is connected to the electric motor directly by the coupling or by the belt and pulley arrangement. The rotation of the motor shaft brings about the rotation of the crankshaft. On the other side the crankshaft is also connected to the connecting rod, which is then connected to the piston at its other end. The rotary motion of the crankshaft is converted into the reciprocating motion of the piston by connecting rod. In case of the multi-cylinder compressors, the number of connecting rods connected to the crankshaft is same as the number of cylinders.

2.24.5 CONNECTING ROD:

The connecting rod is the connecting link between the piston and the crankshaft. On one side the connecting rod is connected to the piston by piston pin and on the other side it is connected to the crankshaft by connecting rod cap. Both these connections of the connecting rod enable converting the rotary motion of the crankshaft into the reciprocating motion of the piston inside the cylinder. The connecting rod is usually made up of carbon steel forging.

2.24.6 SUCTION VALVE AND DISCHARGE VALVE:

Through the suction valve the low pressure refrigerant is sucked inside the cylinder and through the discharge valve the compressed high pressure refrigerant is discharged to the discharge line, from where the refrigerant goes to the condenser. The operation of the suction valve is such that it opens when the piston moves downwards and closes when the refrigerant is being discharged. The discharge valve opens only when the piston reaches a certain level inside the cylinder and the refrigerant has reached the desired level of pressure. When the refrigerant is delivered from the cylinder, the discharge valve closes.

2.24.7 SUCTION AND DISCHARGE PIPELINES:

Through the suction piping the low pressure refrigerant is taken inside the cylinder via the suction valve. The high pressure compressed refrigerant is delivered through the discharge line. [6]

CHAPTER#3

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1 RESEARCH PURPOSE:

Supplier Quality Assurance (SQA) is a very important department of any organization because it is responsible for supplier quality surveillance with established standard of the organization. There may be various issues in the supplier quality assurance of the organization which requires improvement for better supplier quality assurance in the arealike identification of defects in supplier materials.

Therefore SQA was selected as the topic of study in thesis research work. In SQA, its operation and inspection procedure were considered. The refrigerator compressor was taken as the focus of study since it is the center of refrigerator cycle. The role and significance of compressor in refrigerator demands to work on it. So it was chosen as the focus of the study and analysis of the defects identified in compressor was done.

3.2 RESEARCH APPROACH:

In this thesis research work the observation, interview and organizational data available at SQA were used as the methodology for collecting the data. The observation is descriptive/interpretative, i.e. qualitative and it is largely informal. Interview contains open questions. Interviews are non-standardized and are frequently used in qualitative analysis. Additional questions can be asked and some may be questions that have not been anticipated in the beginning of the interview [8]. The some questions which were asked to participant in the interview are mentioned below but their detail discussed in next chapters.

- 1) What are the criteria to issue the certificate of compliance (COC) to supplier?
- 2) What are the problems faced by SQA in inspection?
- 3) What are the number of suppliers both local and import?
- 4) What are the numbers of COC suppliers?

-
- 5) From which companies URIL import compressor?
 - 6) Which type of refrigerator compressor is used in URIL (Dawlance) refrigerator?
 - 7) How many compressors contain in box of a lot?
 - 8) What are the accessories of compressor?
 - 9) What is the cost of compressor?
 - 10) What is the sample size of compressor?
 - 11) What will company do with defected compressors?
 - 12) What are the defects of compressors?
 - 13) What are the reasons for defects in compressors?

CHAPTER # 4

CASE STUDY

4.1 INTRODUCTION TO SUPPLIER QUALITY ASSURANCE (SQA) AT URIL (DAWLANCE):

The SQA Department in URIL (Dawlance) applies all activities related to inspection and testing of material performs at the time of receiving and total number of employees at this department is 15. The organogram of Supplier Quality Assurance department at URIL is shown in fig hierarchically from head of quality to assistant.

The Incharge SQA supervises and monitors the overall activities of SQA. The Incharge operational activity control all the inspection activity carries out at SQA. There are seven assistant Under Incharge operational activity. While Incharge vendor improvement monitors the vendor corrective action. There is one assistant under Incharge vendor improvement. The Incharge customer feedback is responsible for collecting the service centre call rate. There is one assistant under Incharge customer feedback.

Fig 4.1(Organogram of SQA, URIL)

4.2 INSPECTION PROCEDURE OF SQA:

1. The receiving department receives the incoming materials on the gate of factory and sends it to the supplier quality assurance department along with material receiving slip (MRS) by generating it.
2. MRS is a computer generated receipt which shows the material receiving date, quantity, Supplier's name and P.O number and has its own independent number.
3. In case of Certificate of Compliance (COC), Incharge receiving section or his representative verifies the material and send the COC number and/or the attached Certificate of Compliance to SQA which is responsible to feed the MRS in system denoting the COC number. COC is the issuance of permit to suppliers for self-inspection of those parts which meet the quality criteria of URIL (Dawlance).
4. This certificate (COC) issues to supplier upon their frequent good lot and for the purpose of cost save and time save in inspection. This certificate contains supplier name, part description, ITI number, PO number and quantity and lot quantity.
5. COC will be given to suppliers upon their frequent good lot of material as a reward and material will not check, However if there will be a problem in material then URIL will cancel the COC of that supplier shown in fig 4.3
6. So in COC the store receives the material directly from the gate and store generates the MRR (material receiving report).
7. The purpose of SQA department is to inspect the material according to the given requirement.
8. The inspection base is on sampling and sampling is random sampling.
9. The concerned inspector at SQA collects the samples according to sampling plan and inspects the material part as per inspection and test instruction (ITI).
10. ITI is the instruction use to inspect a part or component as per engineering drawing/specification/guidelines. ITI vary from part to part.

11. Without approval from this department the material will not move in the store because there is a policy of URIL to make the inspection of material except COC.
12. Sample test report (STR) is prepared in every sampling in which material is checked visually, functionally and dimensionally as shown in fig 4.4
13. STR is the dimensional and aesthetical report prepared to check the complete dimensions of any part/component. This report contains checking criterion which sub-categorizes into visual check, functional check and dimensional check. In visual check there is an option for standard either the color or ID mark are either within standard or out of standard. In dimensional check there is an option for tolerance either it is within range or out of range.
14. The SQA department cannot check some materials directly like chemicals and electronics. So for that material SQA personnel generate the check form (C Form) as shown in fig 4.5
15. SQA personnel generate RMDN (rejected material disposition notice) if the lot rejects and informs to the concerned buyer for replacement.
16. The SQA department generates RMDN for non-conforming parts/material/products at the time of receiving. This report contains what action URIL takes against the non-conforming parts as shown in fig 4.6
17. SQA personnel generate MSR (material status report) if the lot accepts and handover the material along with the specific MRS to store. The sample of this document is shown in fig 4.7
18. MRS is generated after the sampling inspection. This report shows the status of material by mentioning the accepted quantity and rejected quantity in a lot. This report also contains PO number and date and supplier name. This report also contains that how much time the supplier revises the defects.
19. SQA personnel also generate the quality defect report (QDR) in case if lot rejects and inform to the concerned buyer and monitor the supplier's corrective actions till its closure. The sample of this document is shown in fig 4.8

-
20. The SQA department generates QDR for non-conforming parts/material at the time of receiving and online component rejection of supplier. This report usually define defect category about the material. The inspector inspects the material and note out the defects that are present on the material. This report contain overall information about the item that in which model the item is use or in other word which model part is it. In the defect category there are two options first is functional and second is non-functional. If the defect is functional then there are three sub-categories that are minor, major and critical. After the completion of report, then it is send to the supplier.
21. SQA department also carries out source inspection, the inspection and test of parts at supplier premises and generates SIR (source inspection report) and handover the material to store. SIR is the inspection report which SQA personnel generate at supplier's premises. This report contains source inspection number and date. This report also contains part description.

Fig 4.2(flow chart of inspection procedure of SQA)

Certificate of Compliance

Part Description : _____ Permit # : _____
Purchase Code : _____
Supplier Name : _____
Supplier Code : _____

P.O No. : _____ P.O Qty: _____ Lot QTY: _____

Lot has been inspected as per ITI No. _____ and found acceptable according to URIL standard.

Sign: _____ Dated: _____

Note: If any non-conformity is found during the production cycle, the supplier will bear all responsibility of replacement and associated expenses.

DP-QCR-002.02 REV. 01

ANNEX-2

RECEIVED
COPY

Fig 4.3 (Document of Certificate of Compliance)

 DAWLANCE GROUP OF COMPANIES
SUPPLIER QUALITY ASSURANCE
"C" FORM

SR. NO. _____

TO: _____	Batch (if Required) 1 _____ 2 _____ 3 _____ 4 _____ 5 _____ 6 _____ 7 _____ 8 _____
PO #: _____ RECEIPT NO. _____	
LC #: _____	
DESCRIPTION: _____	
ITEM NO. _____	
SUPPLIER: _____	
RECEIVED QTY: _____	
PLEASE RECEIVE _____ Nos / Kg OF ABOVE MENTION ITEM	
REMARKS _____	
YOUR QUALITY ASSISTANCE IN TESTING IS REQUIRED PLEASE CHECK AND REPORT	
RECEIVED BY _____	INCHARGE / SUPERVISOR
DATE _____	SQA

SAMPLE TEST REPORT

DATE _____

WE HAVE CHECKED ABOVE SAMPLE STATED ACCORDING TO QUALITY STANDARD
RESULT IS MENTIONED BELOW

OK
 REJECT

IN CASE OF REJECT / CONDITIONALLY ACCEPT PLEASE STATE REASON

CHECKED BY : _____ APPROVED BY MFG : _____ APPROVED BY QUALITY _____

DGC- IT- 002, 02 REV.01

Fig 4.5 (Document of C-form)

AWLANCE (PRIVATE) LIMITED
REJECTED MATERIAL AND DISPOSITION NOTICE

Date From : 18-NOV-2009 RMDN No : Receipt No : PO No :
Date To : 18-NOV-2009

RMDN No : 351 Legacy PO : DFL 2 DF
PO Number : 33260 PO Date : 18-SEP-09
Receipt Number : 18288 Receipt Date : 18-NOV-09
Supplier Name : SAMETCO Supplier Number : 384

Item Code : 31-02-400048-0234-00-0003-0000 Rev : Description : SERVICE BASKET RAW FOR DF

Receipt Quantity : 148 UOM : NUMBER Qty Rejected : 148.00
Challan # : Qty Accept : 0.00

Type Of Inspection : Sample

Reason for Rejection							
Sr. No	Fault Detail	Return to Vendor	Use As Is	SCR	RWK	Type of Note	Note Detail
1	BENDING PROBLEM	4.00				RTS	
2	WELDING FAULT	19.00				RTS	BUTT JOINT /WEAK
3	SPOT WELD BROKEN	21.00				RTS	
4	DESHAPE	113.00				RTS	
Total:		148.00					

Inspector Name : ANIRAN Inspection Date : 18-NOV-09
Incharge Name : Incharge Approval Date : 18-NOV-09
Temp Inspector Name :

Material Sign QC Sign Mfg Sign

18-NOV-2009 02:31:29 Page 1 of 1

Fig 4.6 (Document of rejected material and disposition notice)

DAWLANCE GROUP
MATERIAL STATUS REPORT (MSR)

Receipt Number :	Legacy PO :
QC Number :	PO Data :
PO Number :	Receipt Date :
Requisition Number:	LC Number :
Supplier Name :	Supplier Number :

Item Code :	Description :
Receipt Quantity :	Quantity Accepted:
Challan Number :	Quantity Rejected:
Source Inspec No.:	RMDN Number :
Inspection Date :	Revision :
UC#l :	

Remarks :

Inspector Name/Supervisor Name _____ Approved By _____

1/1/2022-22

Fig 4.7 (Document of material status report)

DAWLANCE GROUP OF COMPANIES								
SUPPLIER QUALITY ASSURANCE								
QUALITY DEFECT REPORT(QDR)								
CONTRIL NO	Code	P.O #	RECEIPT #	QTY received	LC #	INSR Ref #	Circuit Report Ref #	
MODEL	PART NAME	DEF QTY	DEF %	RESPONSIBLE DEPTT:	NMDN Ref	Supplier	Org	
Defect Specification.				SUPPLIER				
DESCRIPTION OF DEFECT (Sketch / Picture where necessary) :					DEFECT CATAGEORY			
					Functional		If functional kindly tick	
					Non Functional		Minor Major Critical	
					FIRST TIME DEFECT			
					REPEATED DEF.			
					Stock Checked at time and score			
					Defects Breakup			
					Defect	QTY	Remarks	
TO BE FILLED BY CONCERNED DEPARTMENT								
DEFECT CAUSE (Specific).								
CORRECTIVE MEASURE (Temporary).					DATE			
					SCHEDULE			
					Effective S #/B.Panel No.			
					COMPLETION			
CORRECTIVE MEASURE (Permanent)					DATE			
					SCHEDULE			
					Effective S #/B.Panel No.			
					COMPLETION			
REMARKS: (If any)								
REPORTED BY :		InCharge SQA	Manager SQA	HOD Quality				
(Sign with date)		(Sign with date)	(Sign with date)	(Sign with date)				
Closing Remarks / Action of SQA								
QDR RECEIVED BY		NOTE: Please return this QDR with in 06 days to QCD after completing.						
(Sign with date)								

Fig 4.8(Document of quality defect report)

4.3 PROBLEMS IN INSPECTION AT SQA:

Late supply of material from the supplier may also cause problem in inspection because proper sampling plan does not follows.

The SQA personnel identify some problems which they face in local supplier parts inspection. Some of them mention here.

SQA department faces the problem in inspection for those materials if jig is not available for checking. Then that material moves to every check point for inspection.

Problem # 1, in condenser spacer bolt do not insert properly due to burr in it which may be due to improper moulding.

Problem # 2, there is a problem of rusting in freezer handle pipe which may be due to galvanizing problem.

4.4 SAMPLING PLAN:

To save the time URIL management set the sampling plan for the inspection of material. According to this the supplier quality assurance inspector take the samples from different lots and then inspect them according to the sample level and makes the reject material report and refund the material (only in case of local parts) if there is a rejection. The sample table of inspection is given below:

SUPPLIER QUALITY ASSURANCE (URIL)						
SAMPLING TABLE						
LOT SIZE	MAJOR DEFECTS (AQL-0.65)			MINOR DEFECTS (AQL-6.5)		
	SAMPLE SIZE	ACCEPT	REJECT	SAMPLE SIZE	ACCEPT	REJECT
2 - 8	2	0	1	2	0	1
9 - 15	3	0	1	3	0	1
16 - 25	5	0	1	5	0	1
26 - 50	8	0	1	8	1	2
51 - 90	13	0	1	13	2	3
91 - 150	20	0	1	20	3	4
151 - 280	32	1	2	32	5	6
281 - 500	50	1	2	50	7	8
501 - 1200	80	1	2	80	10	11

1201 – 3200	125	2	3	125	14	15
3201 – 10000	200	3	4	200	21	22
10001 – 15000	315	5	6	315	21	22
15001 – 35000	500	7	8	500	21	22
35001 – 50000	800	10	11	800	21	22
50001 – OVER	1250	14	15	1250	21	22

Table 4.1

4.5 SUPPLIERS:

The supplier of URIL is categorizing into local suppliers and import suppliers. The total number of local suppliers is 110 and total number of imported suppliers is 56. However total number of COC suppliers is 60. COC is only given to local suppliers not to import suppliers due to quality concern.

4.6 FOCUS OF STUDY:

Our focus of study was the defects of refrigerator compressor. A refrigerator compressor is the center of the refrigeration cycle. It works as a pump to control the circulation of the refrigerant, and it adds pressure to the refrigerant, heating it up. Due to compressor role in refrigerator there can be space to study refrigerator compressor defects therefore we choose it as our focus of study. The data regarding compressor defects was analyzed from different aspects.

4.7 COMPRESSOR:

It compresses the gas and supply refrigerant (R-134a) to the system (refrigerator). URIL (Dawlance) imports compressors from three different companies namely, **PANASONIC, DENFOSS and WANBAO** of different HP (1/4, 1/5, 1/6) from Malaysia, Slovakia and China respectively. URIL (Dawlance) have imported Compressors along with its accessories. URIL (Dawlance) uses the reciprocating type of compressor in refrigerator. A reciprocating compressor uses the reciprocating action of a piston inside a cylinder to compress refrigerant. Compressors come in boxes and each box contains 80 compressors and total boxes in a lot can be in between 50-200.

4.7.1 COMPRESSOR ACCESSORIES:

The list of compressor accessories is mention below:

- PTC Relay
- Motor protector
- Running capacitor
- Protector cover
- Clamp
- Cord clamp screw Assy
- Clamp screw
- Cord clamp b
- Fixing screw
- Rubber grommet
- Sleeve
- Name plate

4.7.2 Cost of compressor:

The cost of compressor includes its accessories. The cost of compressor varies from company to company. However in URIL the cost of compressor for **WANBAO** is Rs.4500, **DENFOSS** is Rs.4800 and for **PANASONIC** is Rs.5000.

4.8 INSPECTION PROCEDURE OF COMPRESSOR:

1. Compressors each lot contains 50-200 boxes and each box contains 80 compressors of same model.
2. The sample size for compressor is 5 for whole lot as per their sampling plan.
3. That 5 compressor sends to lab for Oil moisture test (standard below 200 ppm) by moisture titrator machine along with C form and for functional test along with accessories of the compressors for checking weight, dimension and pressure test (Min 1.5 & Max 2 bar) means compressor inside pressure of nitrogen (N₂) and also their fitment.

4. After that compressor is going through consignment testing in which compressors mount in cabinets. 2 cabinets' tests at 43 Oc Ambient and other 3 cabinets test at normal Ambient by running compressor for 70-90 minutes.
5. Then the suction pipe is touch with hand for checking the compressor sound and overcharging problem. The findings of the results (43 oc & normal Ambient) write on C form and deliver the form to SQA.
6. If any discrepancy found in the function of compressor then first they change the relay, overload otherwise change the compressor and scrap the defected one. In case of no discrepancy then compressor will be right according to requirement.

Fig 4.9 (Flow chart of inspection procedure of compressor)

The compressor lot come from supplier is shown in fig 4.10 below:

Fig 4.10 (Lot of compressor)

4.9 DEFECTED COMPRESSORS:

There will be no any re-work to defected compressor. However URIL will scrap the compressor instead of return to supplier due to higher cost of logistics in import compressors. But URIL will inform to supplier about the nature of defect that will compensate the defected quantity of compressors in the next lot.

4.10 COMPRESSOR DEFECTS:

The compressor defects list is mention below which is taking for study:

1. High-ampere
2. Rigidity Fault
3. Suction pipe tube crack
4. Under Charge
5. Oil in/out pipe joint leak
6. Compressor sound
7. Compressor not start

4.11 DATA OF COMPRESSORS DEFECTS:

The data which are collecting for the period of july-12 to july-13 for study of above mention defects are shown below in tabular form and graphical form monthly for all 3 companies. The details of defects of all three companies shown in tabular form below in table 4.2:

MONTH	COMPANIES	HIGH AMPERE	PIPE CRACK	PIPE LEAK	RIGIDITY FAULT	COMPRESSOR NOT START	COMPRESSOR SOUND	LEAK & UNDER CHARGE
JULY-12	PANASONIC	2	1	2	0	0	0	0
	DENFOSS	2	6	0	0	0	0	0
	WANBAO	6	0	1	0	0	0	0
AUG-12	PANASONIC	4	1	0	0	0	0	0
	DENFOSS	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	WANBAO	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
SEP-12	PANASONIC	2	0	2	0	0	6	0
	DENFOSS	2	0	0	2	0	0	0
	WANBAO	23	3	2	0	0	0	0
OCT-12	PANASONIC	3	0	0	0	0	0	0
	DENFOSS	2	0	0	0	0	0	2
	WANBAO	5	0	51	3	0	0	0
NOV-12	PANASONIC	5	1	2	0	0	0	0
	DENFOSS	0	10	0	6	0	0	0
	WANBAO	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
DEC-12	PANASONIC	0	0	2	0	9	0	0
	DENFOSS	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	WANBAO	0	20	0	0	0	0	0
JAN-13	PANASONIC	10	0	6	0	0	0	0
	DENFOSS	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	WANBAO	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
FEB-13	PANASONIC	12	0	8	5	0	0	0
	DENFOSS	0	3	1	0	0	0	0
	WANBAO	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
MAR-13	PANASONIC	18	0	5	0	0	0	0
	DENFOSS	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	WANBAO	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
APR-13	PANASONIC	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	DENFOSS	4	0	3	0	0	0	0
	WANBAO	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
MAY-13	PANASONIC	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	DENFOSS	14	0	32	0	0	0	0
	WANBAO	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
JUN-13	PANASONIC	12	0	4	0	0	0	0
	DENFOSS	4	0	9	0	0	0	0
	WANBAO	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
JULY-13	PANASONIC	4	0	4	0	4	0	0
	DENFOSS	1	6	0	0	0	0	0
	WANBAO	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Table 4.2

4.11.1 DATA OF PANASONIC COMPRESSOR DEFECT:

The tabular data of Panasonic compressor defects is mention below. The graphic form of tabular data is also given below for better understanding of defects. The separate graphs of month wise defects of Panasonic compressors are also shown below:

PANASONIC		
MONTH	SUPPLIER QUANTITY	DEFECTED QUANTITY
JULY-12	3425	5
AUG-12	4145	4
SEP-12	8960	10
OCT-12	2500	3
NOV-12	1760	8
DEC-12	4021	11
JAN-13	6330	16
FEB-13	2720	25
MAR-13	3200	23
JUN-13	1870	16
JULY-13	3659	12

Table 4.3

Fig 4.11

4.11.1.1 DEFECTS IN PANASONIC COMPRESSORS:

The different types of defects identified in Panasonic compressor are presented in graphic form month-wise as below:

Fig 4.12

Fig 4.13

Fig 4.14

Fig 4.15

Fig 4.16

Fig 4.17

Fig 4.18

Fig 4.19

Fig 4.20

Fig 4.21

Fig 4.22

4.11.2 DATA OF DENFOSS COMPRESSOR DEFECT:

The tabular data of Denfoss compressor defects is mention below. The graphic form of tabular data is also given below for better understanding of defects. The separate graphs of month wise defects of Denfoss compressors are also shown below:

DENFOSS		
MONTH	SUPPLIER QUANTITY	DEFECTED QUANTITY
JULY-12	1351	8
SEP-12	460	4
OCT-12	580	4
NOV-12	1190	16
FEB-13	831	4
APR-13	556	7
MAY-13	636	56
JUN-13	714	13
JULY-13	878	7

Table 4.4

Fig 4.23

4.11.2.1 DEFECTS IN DENFOSS COMPRESSORS:

The different types of defects identified in Denfoss compressor are presented in graphic form month-wise as below:

Fig 4.24

Fig 4.25

Fig 4.26

Fig 4.27

Fig 4.28

Fig 4.29

Fig 4.30

Fig 4.31

Fig 4.32

4.11.3 DATA OF WANBAO COMPRESSOR DEFECT:

The tabular data of Wanbao compressor defects is mention below. The graphic form of tabular data is also given below for better understanding of defects. The separate graphs of month wise defects of Wanbao compressors are also shown below:

WANBAO		
MONTH	SUPPLIER QUANTITY	DEFECTED QUANTITY
JULY-12	460	7
SEP-12	580	28
OCT-12	160	59
DEC-12	80	20

Table 4.5

Fig 4.33

4.11.3.1 DEFECTS IN WANBAO COMPRESSORS:

The different types of defects identified in Wanbao compressor are presented in graphic form month-wise as below:

Fig 4.34

Fig 4.35

Fig 4.36

Fig 4.37

CHAPTER # 05

ANAYSIS OF DATA

5.1 COMPARISON OF SUPPLIER QUANTITY WITH DEFECTED QUANTITY AMONG COMPRESSOR COMPANIES:

A comparison was made of supplier quantity with defected quantity among the three compressor companies from July-12 to July-13 as given in the following graph:

Fig 5.1

In the months of July, September, October 2012, supplier quantity and their defects were noted for all three companies. In the months of November 2012, February, June and July 2013, the supplier quantity and defected quantity of Panasonic and Denfoss were noted. In the month of December 2012, supplier quantity and defected quantity of Panasonic and Wanbao were noted. In the months of August 2012 and January and March 2013, the supplier quantity and defected quantity of only Panasonic were noted. In the months of April and May 2013, the supplier quantity and defected quantity of only Denfoss was noted.

5.2 COMPARISON OF DEFECTED QUANTITY AMONG THREE COMPANIES:

The defected quantity of three refrigerator companies was compared from July-12 to July-13 as shown in the graph below:

Fig 5.2

The trend of defected quantity of Panasonic shows that defected quantity was highest noted during the months of February and March 2013. The defected quantity of Denfoss was noted highest in the month of May 2013. The defected quantity in Wanbao was noted highest in the month of September and October 2013.

5.3 ANALYSIS OF DIFFERENT DEFECTS WITH RESPECT TO TOTAL DEFECTS IN EACH COMPRESSOR COMPANY:

The data collected was analyzed month-wise for all three compressor companies. The charts given below highlight percentages of different defects in each compressor company from July 2012 to July 2013. The comparison of defects of compressor companies are given below in percentage with respect to total defects found in each company.

JULY-12:

Fig 5.3

In the month of July-12, three different defects which were high ampere, pipe crack and pipe leak were found in compressors and all the three companies had high ampere defects. In this case of high ampere defects, Wanbao had higher percentage of high ampere defect which was 86% followed by Panasonic which was 40% and Denfoss which was 25%. In case of pipe crack 75% defects were in Denfoss followed by Panasonic which was 20%. The defect of pipe leak was higher in Panasonic compressor which was 40% followed by Wanbao which was 14%.

AUGUST-12:

Fig5.4

In the month of August-2012, the compressor defects were only found in Panasonic compressors. The defects were high ampere and pipe crack which were 80% and 20% respectively

SEPTEMBER-12:

Fig 5.5

In the month of september-12, five different types of defects were identified in compressors which were high ampere, pipe crack, pipe leak, rigidity fault and compressor sound and all three companies had high ampere defect. The high ampere was higher in Wanbao compressor which was 82% followed by Denfoss which was 50% and Panasonic which was 20%. However the defect of pipe crack was only found in Wanbao which was 11%. In case of pipe leak; Panasonic had higher percentage which was 20% followed by Wanbao which was 7%. The defect of rigidity was identified in Denfoss which was 50%. In case of compressor sound 60% defects were found in Panasonic.

OCTOBER-12:

Fig 5.6

In the month of October-12, four different defects were identified in compressors which were high ampere, pipe leak, rigidity fault and leak& undercharge. The defect of high ampere was higher in Panasonic compressor which was 100% followed by Denfoss which was 50%.and Wanbao which was 9%. However the defects of pipe leak and rigidity fault were found only in Wanbao which were 86% and 5% respectively. The leak and undercharge defect was in Denfoss only which was 50%.

NOVEMBER-12:

Fig 5.7

In the month of November-12, the four different defects were identified which were high ampere, pipe crack, pipe leak and rigidity fault. The defects of high ampere and pipe leak were only found in Panasonic compressors which were 63% and 25% respectively. In case of pipe crack defect; the Denfoss had higher percentage which was 62% followed by Panasonic which was 12%. However in case of rigidity fault 38% defects were only found in Denfoss.

DECEMBER-12:

Fig 5.8

In the month of December-12, the three different defects were identified which were pipe crack, pipe leak and compressor not start. The defect of pipe crack was only found in Wanbao compressor which was 100%. However the defects of pipe leak and compressor not start in Panasonic compressors were 18% and 82 % respectively.

JANUARY-13:

Fig 5.9

In the month of January-13 the compressor defects of high ampere and pipe leak were found in Panasonic compressors which were 62% and 38% respectively.

FEBRUARY-13:

Fig 5.10

In the month of February-13, the total four different compressor defects were identified which were high ampere, pipe crack, pipe leak and rigidity fault. The defects of high ampere and rigidity fault were found in Panasonic which were 48% and 20% respectively. In case of pipe leak the Panasonic had higher percentage which was 32% followed by Denfoss which was 25%. However the defect of pipe crack was only found in Denfoss which was 75%, the highest among all defects in this month.

MARCH-13:

Fig 5.11

In the month of March-13 the defect of high ampere and pipe leak were only found in Panasonic compressors which were 78% and 22% respectively.

APRIL-13:

Fig 5.12

In the month of April-13 the compressor defects were identified in Denfoss, the defects were high ampere and pipe leak which were 57% and 43% of defects.

MAY-13:

Fig 5.13

In the month of May-13 the compressor defects of high ampere and pipe leak were found only in Denfoss which were 70% and 30% respectively.

JUNE-13:

Fig 5.14

In the month of June-13, two defects were identified in compressors which were high ampere and pipe leak. The defect of high ampere was higher in Panasonic compressor which was 75% followed by Denfoss which was 31%. In case of pipe leak 69% defects were in Denfoss followed by Panasonic which was 25%.

JULY-13:

Fig 5.15

In the month of July-13, four different defects were identified in compressors which were high ampere, pipe crack; pipe leak and compressor not start. In case of high ampere the Panasonic had higher percentage of defect which was 33%, followed by Denfoss which was 14%. However in case of pipe crack 86% defects were only found in Denfoss. The defects of pipe leak and compressor not start were identified in Panasonic compressor which was 34% and 33% respectively.

5.4 ANALYSIS OF DEFECTS COMPANY WISE:

The data for refrigerator compressor defects, company wise was analyzed. The line graphs for each refrigerator compressor company are shown in graph below:

Fig 5.16

In Panasonic, high ampere defect was seen frequently and highest quantity noted in March 2013. The defect of pipe leak was highest noted in the month of February 2013. The rigidity fault was seen high in the month of February 2013. The defect of pipe crack was highest in the month of August and November 2012.

Fig 5.17

In Denfoss, pipe leak was seen frequently and highest quantity noted in May 2013. The high ampere was seen high in the month of May 2013. The defect of pipe crack was highest noted in the month of November 2012. The rigidity fault was seen high in the month of November 2012.

Fig 5.18

In Wanbao, pipe leak was seen frequently and highest quantity noted in October 2012. The high ampere was seen high in the month of September 2012. The defect of pipe

crack was highest noted in the month of December 2012. The rigidity fault was seen high in the month of October 2012.

5.5 ANALYSIS OF INDIVIDUAL DEFECT:

The data for individual defect was also analyzed. The mean of each defect was obtained for every compressor company. The mean of defects are shown in graphs below:

Fig 5.19

By analysis, the mean graph of high ampere defect had shown that the Wanbao compressor had the highest high ampere defect which had the mean value 11.33, followed by Panasonic which had 7.2 and Denfoss had 4.14.

In the analysis, the mean graph of rigidity fault of Panasonic compressor had shown highest defect of rigidity which had the mean value of 5, followed by Denfoss which had 4 and the Wanbao had value minimum defect which had mean value 3.

In analysis it was found that the Wanbao compressor had the highest defect of pipe leak which had mean value 14, followed by Denfoss which had 10.2 and Panasonic had 4.125.

However the defects of compressor sound and compressor not start were only present in Panasonic and identified two defects.

It was found in analysis that the pipe crack defect had come in Wanbao compressor frequently which had the mean value 11.5, followed by Denfoss compressor which had 6.33. However Panasonic had

of compressor sound and one case of compressor not start during the period July-12 to July-13. The defect of leak & undercharge was only present in Denfoss and 1 defect was found during the study period.

5.6 MAIN REASONS FOR DEFECTS:

The defects of compressors which we study are high ampere, rigidity fault, suction pipe tube crack, oil in/out pipe joint leak, compressor sound, leak & under charge and compressor not start. We sought the reasons of these defects. The reasons of defects were known through the semi-structured interviews of experienced persons identified among the staff dealing with these defects.

The high ampere defect: It is mentioned that the high ampere defect is due to mechanical reason like crankshaft alignment and the other reason is due to overcharging of gas compressor which takes high ampere.

The rigidity defect: It is due to electrical fault like improper connection and it may also happen due to short circuit.

The pipe leak defect: It is due to material problem from supplier side and also happens by mishandling in installation.

The pipe crack: The suction pipe tube crack is due to inferior material.

The compressor not start defect: It is due to non-functioning of compressor accessory (relay).

The compressor sound defect: It is due to unbalancing of spring of inlet and outlet valve of compressor.

The leak and undercharge problem: It is due to pressure and temperature calibration variation.

5.7 DISCUSSION:

The selection of URIL (Dawlance) for thesis research work was due to the market share of Dawlance in refrigerator as one of the premiere home appliances company in Pakistan. Through case study it was found that URIL (Dawlance) had a mechanism for checking the quality of the supplier material. For this they had a department of supplier quality assurance. However URIL had a limited number of suppliers and it was felt that their supplier evaluation criteria was either not properly implemented or not properly set in because in the case study it was found that there were number of defects in imported compressors which were not actually rectified during the study period. There is a room for improvement in this area.

Supplier quality assurance (SQA) is a tool for achieving the satisfaction of market requirements. The case study undertaken was about Supplier quality assurance which maintained the quality of incoming material by identification of defects in material. As shown in the case study, URIL had a separate SQA department. In contrast to that those organization which have not SQA may have a number of defects as no arrangement for inspection or surveillance of supplier material. In the absence of SQA the organization

may suffer a huge number of losses due to defect in products which may effect on company reputation. Moreover in-process defects on material may also bring financial burden due to wastage of material.

In URIL compressors were imported from three companies which were Panasonic, Denfoss and Wanbao. The different defects were identified in the compressor during the study period. During this period mean frequency of pipe leak was the highest followed by high ampere, pipe crack and rigidity while the defects of compressor sound, compressor not start and leak & undercharge were occurred rarely during the study period. The proportion of defects was highest in Wanbao indicating that the Wanbao compressors were of poor quality.

The defects which were identified during the study period may not necessarily to be identified in the next period in URIL. Also the defects which were identified in the URIL may not to be identified in other refrigeration companies' compressors in the Pakistan. The study had limitation of time as it was conducted for under-graduate thesis. With limited number of visits the data collected through semi-structured interviews could not be verified for accuracy.

CHAPTER # 06

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

6.1 CONCLUSION:

1. Frequent numbers of defects were observed during the assembly line even after the SQA inspection.
2. Lack of appropriate and in time communication with supplier was observed at SQA.
3. Monitoring of supplier corrective action of non-conforming material was not observed.
4. Dimensional checking of compressor was not carried out which may cause fitment problem in assembly line.
5. Sample size of five (5) was set for the inspection of compressor for the inspection of compressor for any lot size ranging from 50-200 boxes of 80 compressor each.
6. Inspection and test requirements of SQA for compressor were found inadequate.
7. Classification of supplier was not done.
8. Only three supplier companies of refrigerator compressor were considered.
9. Supplier evaluation was not conducted at SQA.
10. Lack of joint quality planning with supplier was observed.
11. Lack of quality improvement plan.
12. Supplier audit was not carried out at SQA.
13. Supplier selection was not carried out according to latest global standard.
14. During the period of our study the rigidity fault mean was highest in Panasonic.
15. During the analysis period of our study the mean of high ampere defect, pipe leak and pipe crack was highest in Wanbao.
16. During the analysis period, the Panasonic defects trend shows that high ampere defect was seen frequently, followed by pipe leak defect, rigidity fault, while pipe crack defect was seen rarely.

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17. During the analysis period, the Denfoss defects trend shows that pipe leak defect was seen frequently, followed by high ampere defect, pipe crack defect, the rigidity fault was seen rarely.
 18. During the analysis period, the Wanbao defects trend shows that pipe leak was seen frequently, followed by high ampere, pipe crack, the rigidity fault was seen rarely.

6.2 RECOMMENDATION FROM RESEARCH:

As we have analyzed the defects in refrigerator compressor at URIL (Dawlance). This is due to the discrepancy in Supplier Quality Assurance (SQA). The following areas are identified for improvement.

1. SQA should identified and minimize the possible defects of compressor through review of the inspection procedure.
2. SQA should communicate weekly on quality and rejection reporting.
3. SQA should properly monitor the supplier corrective action on non-conforming material.
4. Dimensional checking should also be conducted during the inspection.
5. Sampling plan of compressor should be reviewed and designed on the basis of lot size.
6. Inspection and test requirement of compressors for SQA should be reviewed and re-design according to latest global standards of SQA.
7. Suitable classification of supplier should be conducted with the appropriate criteria.
8. More alternate supplier of compressor should be searched at regional and international level.
9. Supplier evaluation should be carried out according to the established standards of SQA.
10. Joint quality planning should be conducted with suppliers.
11. Quality improvement plans should be conducted on regular basis.

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12. Supplier audit should be conducted on periodic basis.
 13. Supplier selection should be carried out according to the latest global standards of SQA.
 14. Rigidity fault can be minimized by avoided and monitoring the short circuit.
 15. Defects of high ampere, pipe leak and pipe crack can be avoided by minimizing over charging, careful handling and using superior quality of material.
 16. In Panasonic compressor special care should be taken to avoid most frequently occurring high ampere defect.
 17. In Denfoss compressor, most frequently occurring pipe leak defect need special care.
 18. In Wanbao compressor, to avoid most frequently occurred pipe leak defect special care should be taken.

6.3 SCOPE OF RESEARCH:

There is a scope and opportunities for further research in the field of Supplier Quality Assurance since it deals with the identification of defects and inspection of incoming parts provided by suppliers. As the focus was in the area of refrigerator compressor defects, it may assume that the number of defects may increase or decrease at URIL in future and similar situation may occur in any other refrigerator company where such type of studies might have not been conducted or if was conducted but not in a proper manner. There is possibility of other defects which was not found in the study but can be identified in future research work.

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